

Pedagogical Implications of the Resilience Framework

Róbert ERDEI¹, Éva PODLOVICS²

¹(University of Miskolc, Miskolc, Hungary)
robert.erdei@uni-miskolc.hu

²(Tokaj-Hegyalja University, Comenius Institute, Sáropatak, Hungary)
podlovics.eva@unithe.hu

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Abstract: *In this study, we would like to reflect on resilience as a pedagogical tool. As a much-researched notion, it has undergone many changes and additions, though, its basics are surprisingly simple and reachable to anyone. However, it can only come true for young children facing risk in their lives if they are supported by their immediate environment, and by their teachers. We also reflect upon its use in classes where pedagogical reflection and metacognitive strategies can help participants enhance resilient qualities. Finally, we refer to a unique Hungarian program that because of its inclusive processes involves resilience as a side effect. Emphasizing this quality can make a difference in class.*

Keywords: conceptualizing resilience, pedagogical reflection, classroom metacognitive strategies, resilient side effect of Hungarian Talent Programs (AJTP)

Conceptualizing the phenomena

The concept of resilience originally stems from the industry field, which describes specific characteristics in material science and environmental sciences. The concept has evolved significantly since its first use. It is widely used to describe characteristics, outcomes, or reactions in various sciences, such as psychology, education, business, ecology, and many more (McAslan, 2010).

The present paper aims to highlight the significance of the pedagogical implications of the concept of resilience and its associated framework. Although the authors rely on the psychological and philosophical aspects of resilience based on their qualifications and experience, the focus is on how education can reap the rewards of incorporating resilience in its practice at different educational levels and improve the outcomes of children as a result.

Resilience is heavily linked to developmental risks and adversities. One of the most common definitions links resilience to two essential conditions. The first is coping successfully with negative experiences, stress, and adversity and, concurrently, being exposed to significant risk or adversity (Masten & Powell, 2003).

'Doing okay' or managing one's life successfully can be understood in various terms. One such marker is the manifestation of competence across severe problems, diverse aspects of life, or developmental tasks. The lack of problems, mental disorders, or maladaptation is another indicator of successful adaptation and functioning despite adversity. One of the most ominous signs of resilient functioning is the ability to fulfil developmentally significant tasks (Masten, 2001).

Masten (2001) stresses that the term 'resilience' is unsuitable to describe one person's life experiences in general or cannot be considered a trait of the individual during his or her whole life. A person who shows remarkable resilience during his life will not cope with adversities or stress successfully later. Another important consideration is that resilience is only one of the possible outcomes for an individual exposed to risk and difficulties. In contrast, another outcome could be depression or other mental disorders. Additionally, being resilient in one aspect of life does not automatically mean that the same individual can successfully adapt and cope with other domains (Ceglédi, 2012).

A shift can be observed in using the term in recent years. Another perspective gradually replaces adverse outcomes, psychopathology, or the rareness of resilient functioning. Masten describes resilience as 'ordinary magic', which implies that the process of human development can be seen more positively, and resilience is an achievable goal for far more children and individuals than thought previously (Masten, 2001). In this perspective, resilience is linked to the most fundamental human adaptation systems and their normal functioning, such as attachment, problem-solving, the ability to learn, self-efficacy, family functions, organizations in the broader community, or religious and cultural traditions. *Blaustein and Kinniburgh* (2010) support this notion and argue that resilient functioning can be related to all children, at least to a certain extent.

On the other hand, *Rutter* (2000) debates this perspective of resilient functioning. He argues that resilience should be seen as rare as it does not reveal anything about coping with one specific form of stress or other stressors. Moreover, a significant variance can be observed in the responses to adverse life experiences and the recovery process following traumatic life events or significant adversity (Rutter, 2000). *Becvar* (2013) believes resilience is more than recovery after personal trauma or risk. Most individuals can maintain a balance in case of adversity. When one needs help to cope successfully, people tend to prefer interventions focusing on family life or close communities.

How resilience can be perceived or described is still debated. Is it a trait of the personality, a process, or an outcome (see Glantz & Svoboda, 1999)? *Garmezy* (1993) believes that resilience is a personal capacity. Rutter (2000) describes it from the perspective of positive outcomes. According to *Wolin and Wolin* (1993), seven personality traits are related to resilience, forming a personality type. Newer studies accentuate the significance of the process, which is linked to the inner characteristics of the individual and their interaction with the external influences of the environment (Luthar et al., 2000; Smith et al., 2013). Based on this perspective, resilience is not a trait, either present in the individual or not, but a phenomenon or a process manifesting in the interaction between significant risk and adversity *and* successful adaptation (Luthar, 2003).

As mentioned earlier, resilience is only one of the potential options or outcomes for the individual who undergoes severe adversities. Luthar (2003) demonstrated the possible outcomes based on the potentially harmful results and the level of risk and adversity experienced by the individual in a matrix. Based on this matrix, there is a subpopulation of children with elevated levels of adaptation who are not exposed to prominent levels of risk and adversities. This would be the ideal scenario for everybody. However, not all children are so lucky. Another sub-population demonstrates developmental difficulties and adverse outcomes despite low risks and adversities or even the presence of no risk at all. The children exposed to medium to high-level adversities can be grouped into two categories. Those characterized as resilient can demonstrate elevated levels of adaptation and successful coping with adversities and difficulties, while those who cannot overcome risks and adversities are described as vulnerable.

Resilience and Education

Toland and Carrigan (2011) stress that the default situation in human development should be normal development in a supportive environment. Therefore, they consider resilience a normal developmental pathway regardless of prominent levels of difficulties or stress. From a pedagogical perspective, resilience is a desirable and achievable target. As *Podlovics* (2021) highlights, resilience can positively impact children in educational institutions. Resilience in children is an opportunity to master their tasks successfully and cope more effectively. Consequently, the chances of promising outcomes increase, making them more likely to do well (Masten, 2001; Erdei, 2015; Podlovics, 2021).

Educational institutions are perceived as places where risk factors and protective factors might influence children's development. However, exposure to risk occurs under supervised conditions as well but it is possible to manage its effects. Consequently, schools and other institutions work as vaccinations. It is impossible to spare all children from the effects of risk and adversity, although avoiding these as much as possible is advisable. However, if children encounter difficulties and challenges, they can face them in a supportive environment, which can help them cope with and avoid being overwhelmed by risk factors. It is beneficial for children to activate the environment's resources from within (Masten & Obradovic, 2006;

Ceglédi, 2012). *Noltemeyer and Bush* (2013) stress that avoiding all potential risk factors in one's life is usually impossible, but the most significant adversities could be avoided in some cases. However, risk often occurs, and preventing it is not an option anymore. Nevertheless, achieving resilient functioning is a desirable goal in such instances.

It must be noted that regardless of the increased attention and sensitivity toward pupils' problems, the number of those still struggling with one or more aspects and being labeled as 'at-risk' or 'problematic' does not decrease. Unfortunately, teachers and other professionals place too great emphasis on the problems of children, which results in different diagnoses or 'labels'. This phenomenon has been known as the Pygmalion effect. However, it is difficult for children to get rid of those labels, and teachers' attention focuses on the problems of individual pupils instead of the potential hiding in them (Hodge, 2009). *Benard* (2006) stresses the importance of identifying the difficulties and risk factors affecting children to help them appropriately. Properly identifying actual risk factors is the foundation of programs that can help children grow.

Pedagogical practices and learning environments of educational institutions are crucial in pupils' academic success or failure. In their study, *Padron, Waxman, and Huang* (1999) found that resilient pupils spent significantly more time with their tasks and interacted more with their teachers than their nonresilient peers. *Blaustein and Kinniburgh* (2010) argue that it might be ironic to assume that children could demonstrate remarkable resilience when they are most susceptible to traumatic life events, especially during early ages. However, children's adaptation despite risk factors and adversity must extend beyond mere survival. Helping children should include the factors that support healthy development and competent adaptation to the environment surrounding them (*Blaustein & Kinniburgh, 2010*).

One of the most significant protective factors in the lives of children could be the sense of belonging, which they can experience as members of their own families and the concerning educational institutions. A good kindergarten or school can offer children this identification and belonging. This opportunity might be crucial for children exposed to multiple risk factors as they might not have such experiences elsewhere (*Christie et al., 2008*). The sense of belonging might be essential during the transition to school (*Bath, 2009*), as it enables children to form positive and valuable relationships with significant others at home, among their friends, or in educational institutions (*Hart et al., 2007*).

According to *Fallon* (2010), schools and other educational institutions play a crucial role in fostering development among children. To fulfill this kind of duty, schools should have unique characteristics, such as having strong leadership, high expectations toward their pupils, stressing the importance of developing basic skills, providing a stable environment, and continuously and thoroughly evaluating pupils' progress. One of the most significant protective factors is a meaningful and strong bond with one or more caring and loving adults, according to *Laurson and Birmingham* (2003). Teachers and other educators can provide such relationships for their pupils.

Various attempts were made to describe the characteristics of resilient children, which would be necessary to designate the most relevant aspects of pedagogical interventions to foster the resilience of children. The findings of Masten (2001) suggest that resilient children have more resources than their vulnerable peers who experience the same levels of risk. Additionally, they have more competent adults around them, better problem-solving skills, and a higher level of general cognitive functioning. *Smokowski and colleagues* (1999) found that resilient children have more manageable temperament than their vulnerable peers, better social competence, optimism regarding the future, and higher levels of adaptability and responsiveness. They tend to be optimistic and have faith in a positive future. *Rahman* (1999) stresses the importance of the lack of behavioral problems despite being exposed to adversity. In this sense, resilient children demonstrate competence and proactively approach problems instead of solely reacting to adverse life events. They tend to perceive difficulties as challenges they can overcome and feel they have control over their destiny. Fallon (2010) adds that resilient children can elicit positive attention from adults, have a flexible approach to problem-solving, and perceive their life experiences in a positive frame. *Mayr and Ulich* (2009) also stress the importance of eliciting positive responses from others as a sign of resilience. According to *Biscoe* (1999), resilient individuals are usually aware of the trouble and need to ask for help.

Moreover, it is possible to enhance resilience through practice and thinking processes. Goal-setting and future orientation also play a crucial role in resilience (Biscoe, 1999; Benard, 1991). Mayr and Ulich (2009) add that resilient children can delay instant gratification, are concentrated and able to persist, are curious, like new experiences and explore the world around them, and are characterized by an empathic and prosocial stance toward others.

Numerous studies suggested that it is possible to develop traits in children linked to resilience or create the conditions of resilient functioning (see Masten, 2001; Masten & Powell, 2003; Fallon, 2010; Podlovics, 2021). Benard (2006) stresses that children are born with innate resilience and can develop social competence, problem-solving skills, critical awareness, autonomy, and goal setting. *Alvord and colleagues* (2003) offer practical advice to schools, which can help to develop and enhance the resilience of pupils, such as allowing connections, helping each other, keeping a daily routine, taking a break, learning to care about yourself, continuing toward the achievement of your goals, maintain a positive self-image, keep a long-term perspective, and accept that change is part of life. Additionally, Laursen and Birmingham (2003) described seven characteristics of caring adults that help foster resilience among children: trust, attention, empathy, availability, reinforcement, respect, and virtue. *Wustmann* (2004) emphasizes the features of interactions between adults and children that contribute to the development of resilience. These are a generally positive attitude toward children, reactivity in the care for children, mutual interactions by the children's level of development, attention, and emotional support during the child's activities, various and frequent interactions, and the initiation of various activities.

Borden, Schultz, Herman, and Brooks (2010) stress the importance of training methods for parents to promote positive parental practice, effective problem-solving, the consistency and predictability of parenting, the increase of family cohesion, and the identification of support systems available to families. These characteristics of families are also beneficial for children.

The situation in schools

We have just been reading that resilience can be fostered in the educational context, however, *Hanson and colleagues* (2021) emphasize that little attention has been paid to enhancing the engagement factors of the school-related social-emotional resources (e.g. resilience or self-worth) either in schools or in the academic and clinical environments. Therefore, it is challenging to expect it from teachers and educators, especially without proper preparation (Stoiber & Gettinger, 2011). However, after such training, the teachers' competence, and extent of resilience among children with challenging or problematic behaviors increased. At the same time, their behavioral difficulties were reduced. Toland and Carrigan (2011) also stress the importance of fostering resilience in schools. *Malindi and Machenjedze* (2012) found that commitment to the school is a positive indicator of resilient functioning, as it can help them retain their status as a child and keep them within the boundaries of formal education. *Ungar and Liebenberg* (2013) found that every child can function normally when exposed to normative stress levels and difficulties. However, some children can maintain such functioning when they face elevated levels of distress and adversity.

A pedagogical tool for classroom resilience can be the teachers' improvement of their teaching activities and habits, in one word, their reflectivity. The idea was well defined by *Dewey* (1910) who highlighted its usability in the educational context. Since then, it has long been supported by many authors. *Zeichner* (1988) explained the benefits and pitfalls of the then-novel initiative spreading around the US in the 1980s and ended up with the conclusion that its efficacy is more likely reachable in a more equal society. *Navaneedhan* (2012) emphasized the role of mental tools such as visual images and metaphorical thinking in reflective teaching that make learning more enjoyable and therefore more lasting for the recipient. *Geng and colleagues* (2019) collected the reflections of pre-service teachers whose identities but also assumptions about their own teaching directions and approaches changed with their practice periods at schools.

From the abundance of viewpoints on reflectivity, I mention *Urbán and Szivák*, who say that reflective thinking is a cognitive mechanism that goes hand in hand with professional development (Urbán & Szivák, 2022). *Szivák* (2010) previously analyzed the process itself, adding that reflectivity includes the pedagogical activity, analytical thinking, and practice of teachers that together ensure the constant self-monitoring and improvement of teachers' and students' educational and fostering processes in classrooms. Further, she says that reflectivity is such learnable lesson for teachers, that can be improved with practice. Its two primary directions stem from the pedagogues who can monitor their personalities and

activities (with self-reflection or lesson analysis with colleagues), and also the students of the class. It is added that reflective thinking is based on prior experiences, values, preconceptions, and the acquired system of professional capacities of teachers. As part of this reflective professional skill, with analytical abilities, we recognize, define, deconstruct, and analyze educational problems, uncover their reasons, construct new problem-solving methods, and think over the consequences. All of them can be improved with practice and are related to resilience.

The reflectively 'good pedagogue' shifts from being a knowledge expert to an expert in pedagogy (Machost & Stains, 2023), has suitable personal characteristics (e.g., understanding, open-minded, sympathetic, flexible) and experiences but also approved theoretical knowledge (Szivák, 2010). If these crucial positive factors work in schools, students who have lost interest in one or other subjects or are 'just' adolescents and lag due to having problems can be spotted and recognized. To detect the underlying problems openness, realistic evaluation, and situational analysis are required from the teachers.

Another applicable tool in the classroom can be metacognition and teaching its different techniques (Taskó, 2015). At first sight, metacognition might frighten e.g. primary school teachers away due to the age-related and varied cognitive capacities of children. However, neither differences nor manifold teaching experiences can remove the potential of using metacognitive strategies in class. Consequently, though, definitions of metacognition like 'acquired knowledge about cognitive processes' or 'knowledge that can be used to control cognitive processes' (Livingston, 2003; Moritz & Lysaker, 2018) may estrange many participants, the use of it can bring success in the diverse classes. Accordingly, teaching metacognitive strategies pays off, and more importantly, is also learnable. Teaching metacognitive techniques can help students coordinate their studies to accomplish their goals with effective learning strategies. Complex, reflective thinking can be learned from the junior section of primary school in Math and Reading classes (for instance, reading strategies make it possible to understand and organize texts). Furthermore, they also help to improve attention, memory, communication, and learning (Moir et al., 2020).

As a related and successful working method in Hungary, I would like to summarize some points of the János Arany Talent Program (AJTP). It is part of the social inclusion strategy of the government and is meant to maintain inclusivity through its direct aim to help socially disadvantaged but talented children conquer their drawbacks with the help of education (European Commission, 2023). According to *Fehérvári and Varga (2018)*, its profile further details that the program works nationwide as an interventional source against early school leaving, it also understands and reflects upon the accumulation of different social disadvantages in one's life (intersectionality) and counterbalances with compensatory services. *Fuszek (2014)* gives a brief but thorough account of the Hungarian National Talent programs, including AJTPs, and concludes that the programs have been successful nationwide thanks to the activity of NGOs, constant public support, effective utilization of EU funds, and responsible sharing. Participants' insight shows that AJTPs offer certificates (ECDL certificate, B2 language certificate, driving license) that make the life of the students

easier, additionally preparing them for higher educational studies (Pécsi Kodály Zoltán Dormitory, 2023).

Fehérvári and Varga (2020) add in their analysis that the program surveys the participants' resilience, and as a result, concludes that the basis of the students' successful adaptation is the real inclusive attitude of schools. The program relies on the basic cognition of resilience, namely, the phenomena that nurture the most fundamental human adaptation systems (Masten, 2001). Consequently, participants in the program pay special attention to their reinforcement in class (e.g., individual support and development or creating and sustaining good relationships and bonds between teachers and students). Other results of the program analysis are the need for professional knowledge and attitude of the involved teachers (flexible acceptance and reaction towards differences of students), the ability for reflection, cooperation of participants (program leaders, teachers, students, parents, experts), taking responsibility by everyone concerned, equal participants, and equity. The overall result of the nationwide program is that structured and mutual efforts can bring results in schools.

Nevertheless, resilience has a price, as several studies have demonstrated. Constant struggles with adversities and complex life events can lead to internal distress (Masten, 1999). Rahman (1999) believes that the successful coping demonstrated by resilient children comes at the price of losing some of their emotional, behavioral, cognitive, and social potential. Masten and Powell (2003) found that young people who experienced war in their country suffered from the consequences of posttraumatic stress, experienced deep sadness, and were emotionally unbalanced. However, they were able to fit in an unfamiliar environment, make new friends, and get on with their lives. *Gordon Rouse and colleagues* (1998) also found higher levels of depression and anxiety among resilient individuals compared to low-risk groups. Alvord and colleagues (2003) argue that higher levels of distress and sadness are natural among resilient children, considering the difficulties, traumas, or losses they face compared to their peers who do not have such experiences. Despite such negative consequences, we agree with *Punamäki and colleagues* (2011), who believe that one of the core features of resilient children is their good mental health despite the difficulties and traumas they have been facing.

Summary

In this study, we tried to reflect on the many changes of resilience as an interrelated term usable in pedagogical practice. We believe dealing with this question in educational institutions can bring another 'super tool' into the everyday lives of children who otherwise cannot be helped by adults. We also emphasized the rich content of the notion and its possible methodological aids in schools and exemplified a program run in Hungary successfully. Paying attention to new and usable psychological insights has always been important. At schools and in life, too. It is possible to enhance the resilience of pupils with the use of pedagogical methods. A resilience framework in the context of pedagogy holds significant implications for fostering the development and well-being of students. This framework acknowledges the dynamic nature of resilience and its potential as a

transformative tool in educational settings. Educators can embrace resilience as a multifaceted concept beyond mere individual characteristics. It recognizes the interconnectedness of personal, social, and environmental factors. Educators can adopt a comprehensive approach that considers the diverse dimensions of a student's life. Resilience can be embedded in the curriculum; resilience education could be a core component of the learning experience. Design lessons that focus on academic content and incorporate activities promoting emotional intelligence, critical thinking skills, and coping mechanisms. This can be achieved through project-based learning, case studies, and interactive discussions. An essential aspect of using the resilience framework in education is cultivating a supportive school culture, which fosters a school atmosphere that values and prioritizes resilience by creating a supportive environment where students feel safe to express themselves, seek help, and learn from challenges. The involvement of parents and communities can also be perceived as a crucial factor in fostering resilience. The resilience framework recognizes the importance of collaboration between schools, parents, and the broader community in building resilience. The use of flexible pedagogical strategies is another vital component, such as acknowledging the diverse learning needs of students, adopting flexible pedagogical strategies, and offering varied teaching methods that cater to different learning styles and allow for personalized learning experiences. This flexibility accommodates the individual strengths and challenges of each student, contributing to the development of resilience. By embracing a resilience framework in pedagogy and executing these implications, educators can contribute significantly to the holistic development of students, empowering them to navigate life's challenges with confidence and adaptability.

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